

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Cells up-regulate ERBB2 and PPDPF in response to CDK4/6 inhibition.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The tumor growth factor PPDPF was induced in cells following pharmacologic inhibition of CDK4/6, as was the EGFR family growth factor molecule ERBB2 (HER2).